

EFFECT OF RADIO CAMPAIGN IN PROMOTING EXCLUSIVE BREASTFEEDING AMONG WOMEN IN RURAL AREAS (A STUDY OF RESIDENTS IN ENUGU NORTH AND SOUTH FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY)

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Abstract

The focus of this research was on Effect of Radio Campaign in Promoting Exclusive Breastfeeding among Women in Rural Areas (A Study of residents in Enugu North and South Federal Constituency). The ultimate aim of the study was to assess the extent to which radio campaign is used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency and to find out whether radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas. The researcher adopted the Agenda Setting Theory and the Health Belief Model as the theoretical framework of the study. The survey research method was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 1033560. A total of 400 copies of questionnaire were administered to the sample of the study while 375 were successfully returned for statistical analysis. The data was analysed using tables, frequencies and percentages for the demography of respondents and research questions. The hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square formula. Findings of the study revealed that Radio campaign is extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency. It was also discovered that Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas. However, Women in rural areas do not comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns. Part of the recommendations of the study was that Frequent and constant portrayal of information about exclusive breastfeeding should be disseminated to nursing and expecting mothers as to create more access to information on good health care practices. Also, radio as well as other broadcast channels should adopt a more strategic approach towards mobilising nursing and expectant mothers towards proper infant and maternal health care practices which exclusive breastfeeding is part of.

Introduction

This research problem aims to determine the efficacy of radio campaigns in encouraging the use of exclusive breastfeeding by women in rural regions, with a particular focus on how it will affect their knowledge and awareness levels, attitudes, and behavior and the overall effects on the wellbeing of mothers and children. It is only possible that effective communication takes place when the right message is conveyed through the right channels to the right audience at the right time. Radio broadcasting has remained an instrument of relevance in mobilization, sensitization, education, information, and entertainment of mass people worldwide (Okeke, Chibuike and Ono, 2021).

Radio broadcasting can be defined as the transmission of audio signals with possible metadata by radio waves to receivers which are utilized by the general population (Philips, 2020). In Africa, oral traditions have also been spread into rural villages, towns and cities with the proliferation of cheaper transistor radio sets, and have served to break the barrier of illiteracy and information poverty. Although there is the development of internet and social media platforms, radio has continued to have a more balanced accessibility across demographic groups (Conroy-Krutz, Amakoh and Amewunou, 2024).

Radio has over the years played a significant role on human and societal development in the developing nations like Nigeria. It has been instrumental in the mobilization of the rural community, democratic mobilization and the enhancement of health programs like family planning. Because of the misinformation that is prevalent, radio is still seen as a reliable source of verified information, thus the reason why it has remained popular in Africa (Mutsaka and Satchel, 2023). Nursing mothers can be equipped with maternal and infant health information by using well planned radio programmes which offer local socio-cultural realities. Radios are cheap, portable, can use battery power, and do not need any literacy, and thus are good tools to use in mass health communication, and approximately three-quarters of the global population has ready access to broadcast technology (Brooke, 2024).

Agenda setting and gate keeping are other ways in which the media influence the discourse of the people. Constant messaging of particular messages implies they are relevant to the social wellbeing such as the message on exclusive breastfeeding (Bosch, 2022). Exclusive breastfeeding means that a mother only feeds her child breast milk within the first six months, with the exception of any supplements prescribed by the doctor (Davis, 2020; Centre for Disease Control, 2022; 2023). Its advantages are fully reported (Villines, 2023; Issaka et al., 2017), although in Nigeria, the practice is low, with 29 percent of newborns being exclusively breastfed (Adejoro, 2023). This highlights the importance of evaluating the role of radio in enhancing maternal and infant health especially in Enugu urban.

Statement of the Problem

Many medical experts, including the American Academy of Paediatrics (AAP) and the American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists, strongly recommend breastfeeding exclusively (no formula, juice, or water) for 6 months. After the introduction of other foods, it recommends continuing to breastfeed through the baby's first year of life (Taylor and Cameron, 2023). Improving maternal and child health, one of the key UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), is a major challenge in sub-Saharan Africa. Exclusive breast-feeding contributes significantly to child survival and development, but many mothers in Africa do not exclusively breastfeed their infants (Otim, et al., 2022). Exclusive breastfeeding has been consistently recommended by the WHO, based on empirical evidence of its protective effects on illness incidences. Primary care physicians, especially in low and middle income countries, provide comprehensive care to the mother and infant by assessing nutrition, providing anticipatory guidance and treating infections. Factors that affect the mothers' ability to exclusively breast-feed can be loosely grouped into personal and institutional issues. Personal factors such as occupation or levels of education may affect a mother's breast-feeding practices. This is consistent with findings in other studies suggesting that mothers who are not engaged in formal employment had more time to breastfeed as compared to those that are formerly employed (Nkrumah, 2016). Limitations on breast-feeding at workplace may be a contributory factor (Otim, et al., 2022).

Based on the foregoing, the radio being the most used media channel in rural areas such as Enugu North Federal Constituency should be deployed as a means of campaigning and sensitising the rural dwellers about the importance and significance of exclusive breastfeeding especially in a language and dialect the people understand hence the researcher is poised to fill the gap in this study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is on Effect of Radio Campaign in Promoting Exclusive Breastfeeding among Women in Rural Areas (A Study of residents in Enugu North and South Federal Constituency). The following are the specific objectives of the study:

1. Assess the extent to which radio campaign is used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency.
2. Find out whether radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas.
3. Ascertain whether women in rural areas comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns.

Research Questions

The research questions for this study are:

1. To what extent is radio campaign used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency?
2. Does radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas?
3. Do women in rural areas comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns?

Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses for this study are:

Hypothesis One

H₁: Radio campaign is extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency.

H₀: Radio campaign is not extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency.

Hypothesis Two

H₂: Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas.

H₀: Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding do not have significant effect on women in rural areas.

Hypothesis Three

H₃ Women in rural areas comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns.

H₀ Women in rural areas do not comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns.

Literature Review

Concept of Radio Broadcasting

Broadcasting involves transmission of useful information, ideas, knowledge, attitudes, feelings, etc., in form of signals through the airwaves to a heterogeneous and widely dispersed audience simultaneously. It can also be conceived as the dissemination or spreading of information, facts and ideas to the general public either in audio or both audio and visual. The mass media engender and provide the communication required for effective governance, politics and overall development of other facets of the society, (Aliede & Ogodo, 2018).

Radio is a wireless transmission that only has the audio element (Ajisafe, 2021). Thus the radio can only be listened to. This nature of radio makes the production of programs cost-effective because few pieces of equipment are required than television. Furthermore, radio receivers are often simplistic in nature thus cheap and affordable, especially to rural people. Battery-operated radio sets make users less dependent on electricity supply and the medium is portable. Portability of the medium ensures that listeners incorporate the medium into their occupations.

Radio cuts across illiteracy and inadequate infrastructure that tend to restrict the print media. It is the most popular mass media in most of the developing nations since it is inexpensive, portable and it is not hard to operate. In Nigeria, radio has been one of the most important sources of political information and engagement since the colonial era up to date in democracy (Olaniru, Olatunji, Ayandele and Popoola, 2019). Radio has been found to affect the campaigns and delivery of political manifestoes (Tham, Wenn, Ong and Lim, 2020). Despite its influence being dependent on the contextual factors, it still influences the discussion of governance and politics (Okinda, Nyambuga

Onovo. Effect of Radio Campaign in Promoting Exclusive Breastfeeding among Women in Rural Areas (A Study of Residents in Enugu North and South Federal Constituency)

and Ojwang, 2020). Traditional radio is also dependable and inclusive because of illiteracy and unequal access to the internet (Nkoala et al., 2024).

Concept of Exclusive Breastfeeding

The Mammary glands in the breast produce milk via a complex of tubes tied to the nipple (Davis, 2020). Breastfeeding means the act of feeding a child with breast milk either through direct feeding or by using expressed milk and is usually affected by social views (Taylor & Cameron, 2023).

Exclusive breastfeeding refers to a situation in which an infant does not consume water or other foodstuffs, but only breast milk (except for drugs or supplements prescribed by a doctor) (Hassan and Hossain, 2023). Young babies without breastfeeding are at risk of becoming sick and developing developmental issues (Pitman and Berrtt, 2007 in Iheanacho et al., 2021).

The World Health Organization suggests initial breastfeeding of the first six months. The rate is between 23.7 percent and 56.5 percent in sub-Saharan Africa (Issaka et al., 2017). In Nigeria, the rates rose by 17 per cent to 29 per cent (Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey, 2019). Poor compliance leads to less than five fatality and diarrhea cases (Ogbo et al., 2015). Lack of breastfeeding by mothers increases their risks of having chronic diseases, and newborn babies are at risk of being infected and developing long-term health complications (Abdulla et al., 2022; Black, 2024).

Breastfeeding: Knowledge and Practices among Nigerian Women

Breast milk is very much thought to be the best form of food that infants should get during the initial six months of their lives. Child mortality is also a worldwide issue and it has been seen that a large percentage of the under five deaths would be prevented by better coverage of exclusive breastfeeding. Despite the improvements in the rates of exclusive breastfeeding during the last 20 years, the global coverage remains lower than the target that the UNICEF recommends as universal (Joel, 2023).

It has been found that the knowledge on exclusive breastfeeding is usually high among women in most countries, but actual practice is often lower than the recommendations (Swigart et al., 2017). The culture of men in Nigeria regarding the exclusivity of breastfeeding is considered to be relatively low, which is considered to undermine the spousal support and affect mothers in terms of adherence to the behavior.

The World Health Organization estimates that only 43 percent of all babies in the world start breastfeeding within the first hour of life, and only 40 percent of infants who are under six months old breastfeed exclusively (WHO, 2020). In sub Saharan Africa, the early initiation varies between 37.8 and 69.3 percent whereas exclusive breastfeeding varies between 23.7 and 56.5 percent (Issaka et al., 2017).

According to national data in Nigeria, infants below six months of age are only breastfed by a mere 29 percent (National Population Commission, 2019). Exclusive breastfeeding rates are not optimum yet over 70 percent of women in southwest Nigeria breastfeed up to one year. The exclusive breastfeeding practised by urban women was only 35.9 percent and by rural women was 10 percent in the southeast (Balogun et al., 2017).

Likewise, a longitudinal study conducted in Ibadan revealed that twelve months later no babies of urban elite women were still breastfeeding, with 100 and 80.8 percent of children of the rural poor and the urban poor respectively (Adewuyi, 2016). These differences demonstrate socioeconomic and contextual factors of breastfeeding behaviour.

Issues Associated with Exclusive Breastfeeding

The sociocultural, economic, psychological, and physical issues influence exclusive breastfeeding. The sociocultural factors take the form of maternal education, level of income, employment and family beliefs. There are also psychological reasons, including a fear of becoming unattractive and

stress, as well as physical issues, including breast enlargement and a disease (Utami et al., 2019). There is also little counselling by health workers that will enhance accurate knowledge.

The misunderstandings are such common assumptions that breast milk is not enough, that marital insecurity, the desire to feed infants through the formula as it is convenient, and that infants gain weight. Partners and relatives of mothers at times discourage exclusive breastfeeding (Wood and Qureshi, 2017). Other factors are also the lack of maternity leave, workplace pressure, the need to introduce water early in the pregnancy, and working mother fatigue (Diji et al., 2017; Valizadeh et al., 2017).

According to the United States Department of Agriculture (2024), challenges encountered include sore nipples, low milk supply issues, engorgement, infection, nursing strike, exhaustion, emotional distress, and social judgment, which are practical. These issues show that knowledge alone does not mean long term practice without supportive systems.

Importance of Exclusive Breastfeeding

From Exclusive breast feeding is better in terms of the survival of the infants and maternal health at a public health standpoint. Hassan and Hossain (2023) forecast that the world coverage can go to 50 percent by 2025, despite existing inequalities. Although formula feeding may be sufficient when population needs it, scientific studies are constantly related to breastfeeding and its various advantages.

Breastfeeding helps mothers to lower the risk of breast cancer, ovarian cancer, type 2 diabetes, and hypertension (Abdulla et al., 2022). In the case of infants, breast milk contains antibodies which protect against infection and also helps to prevent asthma, respiratory infections, diarrheal diseases, diabetes, and sudden infant death syndrome. Non exclusive breastfeeding has been a leading cause of child mortality especially in Asia and Africa (Abdulla et al., 2022).

Breastfeeding also aids emotional wellbeing through building of bonding, reducing stress levels, and comforting infants. It is easily accessible, economical and nutritionally beneficial after the initial year of life.

Disadvantages

Breastfeeding has no medical disadvantages after one year as long as there is a sufficient supplementary feeding. Nevertheless, there may be a problem with social stigma, time limitations, work restrictions, and fertility issues.

Media and the Promotion of exclusive Breastfeeding

The media is central to influence health behavior. It informs women about the advantages and effective methods concerning exclusive breastfeeding (Catalan Matamoros and Penafiel Saiz, 2019). The impact of media exposure is on attitudes and perception of norms and intentions towards behavioral changes (Iheanacho et al., 2021). Especially electronic media has been effective in raising awareness among working mothers (Utami et al., 2019).

The World Health Organization (2022) points out the importance of responsible reporting, discussion in the population, responsibility, and digital platform growth. In World Breastfeeding Week 2022, leaders of the UNICEF and WHO encouraged governments to improve policies supporting breastfeeding, educate health workers, restrict marketing of formula, and promote policies building family friendly workplaces (WHO, 2022).

Radio Programmes for Empowering Nursing Mothers

The messages on exclusive breastfeeding are spread on television, radio, print, and digital sources (Iheanacho et al., 2021). Radio is also very useful among the rural population who have little access to

other media (Eze, 2020). It provides culturally competent information using local languages, drama, music, and interactive discussions, resulting in increased awareness and engagement.

The availability of radio can enable the extension officers and health educators to offer practical advice, engage in a conversation and clear up the misunderstandings. Since under nutrition is one of the causes of the death of millions of children each year, optimal breastfeeding may avoid a significant percentage of these deaths (Atimati, 2018). The fact that broadcasting is in local dialects also enhances understanding and acceptance.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two theories and they are the Agenda Setting Theory and the Health Belief Model.

Agenda Setting Theory

The Agenda setting theory proposes that the media dominates the perception of issues importance to the people. Radio can influence the priority awareness of mothers by focusing on the concept of exclusive breastfeeding (Okenwa, 2002; McCombs & Shaw, 1972). The increase in visibility leads to awareness and maybe a change in policy and behavior (Rodman, 2010).

Health Belief Model

The Health Belief Model is used to explain the health behavior in terms of perceived risk, benefits, barriers and self efficacy (Amannah & Ugwu, 2018 as cited in Mbiereagu & Etumnu, 2021). Media campaigns are action clues, through which the mothers can weigh the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding against perceived challenges.

Application of the Theories to the Study

According to the Agenda Setting Theory, there will be an increase in the perceived importance of exclusive breastfeeding among nursing mothers when there is a regular increase in the amount of radio time assigned to this activity. Health Belief Model helps to prove the assumption that mothers hearing persuasive messages on the radio can acquire positive attitudes and stronger intentions to practice exclusive breastfeeding, especially in rural communities.

Empirical Reviews

Here, empirical research that is coherent to the current study is examined, especially those that concern community radio, broadcast media and exclusive breast-feeding habits in the African and Nigerian settings. The review demonstrates trends in methodology, theoretical focus, findings and the recommendations as well as gaps, which prove the necessity of the present research.

Adams (2024) investigated the role of community radio in rural development in Nigeria. The research approach that was used in the study was library-based research method because the data generation relied on available literature. It was based on the Democratic Participant Theory, which focuses on the participation of the grassroots in the communication processes. The results showed that community radio has a positive effect on rural development in various thematic dimensions, such as education, political suitability, agricultural transformation, participatory democracy, giving voice to marginalized groups, offering platforms on local discussions, exploiting the vulnerable rural people, and fostering good governance. This research paper found that radio programming in these thematic areas should be intensified by the local authorities in order to develop rural and communities. The topicality of the given study is that it proves the usefulness of radio as an effective means of development communication that can help to change social and health outcomes on the grassroots level.

Yakubu et al. (2023) examined exclusive breastfeeding awareness and behavior among the nursing mothers in the identified healthcare institutions in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria. The research was a descriptive cross-sectional study that involved the use of structured questionnaires that were conducted in Barau Dikko Teaching Hospital and Gwamna Awwal general hospital. The simple

random sampling was employed to select the participants in four consecutive weeks in each hospital. The SPSS version 16 was used to analyze the data. The results indicated that majority of the respondents were aged 21-30 years of age and the greatest source of information on breastfeeding was the antenatal clinics. A large percentage of the respondents were found to be well aware of exclusive breastfeeding with many of them starting to breastfeed during the first hour after birth and a high number practicing exclusive breastfeeding of six months. Nevertheless, the perceived lack of enough milk, cultural beliefs, social expectations, and fear of body changes were some of the obstacles to the optimum practice. The research mentions the significance of long-term health education and the need to deal with sociocultural myths.

Joel (2023) examined the role of men in early exclusive breastfeeding in Nigeria through a qualitative research design study. The purposely chosen thirty-two recent fathers in four states were sampled and a series of four focus group discussions took. The data were analyzed by thematic analysis assisted by NVivo software. The results indicated that cultural beliefs and gender role perceptions, low level of knowledge, and access to breastfeeding information decreased the involvement of men in exclusive breastfeeding. This is because many participants saw breast feeding as the women role. The research suggested the use of inclusive interventions to support both males and females to promote exclusive breastfeeding. Through this piece, we see the significance of gender relations and access to information as a determinant of breastfeeding practices.

A cross sectional study in the Mulago Hospital, Kampala, Uganda was completed by Etim et al. (2022) to determine factors which affect exclusive breastfeeding at the age of the first six months of infant life. The mixed methods were used and involved 362 lactating mothers and health workers. The sampling was simple random and data was analyzed with EpiInfo and SPSS. The findings showed that socio demographic variables including age and education played a great role in the readiness and capability of mothers to exclusively feed their infants. Most of the awareness was acquired through health centers and this restricted the accessibility to mothers who had no access to such centers. Also, there were many health workers who were unaware of the national infant feeding. The paper suggested the reinforcement of community health systems and educating health workers about the policies of breastfeeding. Its results point to institutional and structural influences on the outcome of breastfeeding.

The study by Penugonda et al. (2022) aimed to investigate the effect of exclusive breastfeeding on prevalent infant diseases in a prospective observational study. Births of healthy term infants were monitored up to six months, and mothers noted feeding patterns and episodes of illness on structured diary cards. The SPSS IBM statistics 22 was used to analyze the data. Exclusive breastfeeding at the age of six months was not ideal. The rate of illnesses was much lower in exclusively breastfed infants than in non-exclusively breastfed infants especially after the ten weeks. The odds of illness among solely breastfed infants were lower, which was proved by logistic regression analysis. The research was concluding that it would be necessary to strengthen in the early initiation and continuation strategies in order to enhance child health outcomes.

Ajisafe (2021) paid attention to the tool of national development, radio. The research highlighted community radio as a tool of information distribution, education and sustainable development. It also emphasized on its role in enhancing animal and human health within the remote African communities. The paper recommended the government to adopt and increase community radio programs, which had influences on the health and wellbeing of the rural population. This asserts the role of radio in being used to contribute to the public health campaigns, such as campaigns on exclusive breastfeeding.

Iheanacho et al. (2021) investigated the effects of broadcast media campaigns on the awareness of exclusive breastfeeding. The research was based on the Health Belief Model and employed survey as its design with the sample of 385 participants chosen among the population of more than 555,000 according to the multistage sampling. The data were gathered through questionnaire. The results

indicated moderate levels of awareness of broadcast campaigns, high ratings of exclusive breastfeeding campaigns as the public enlightenment programs and moderate adherence to exclusive breastfeeding behavior. The research suggested that more awareness campaigns and exposure on the breastfeeding messages to women through broadcast media should be strengthened.

Akadiri and Odelola (2019) also examined the breastfeeding habits of mothers in Southwest Nigeria. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data on 340 people attending parous antenatal clinics in Ogun State and analyzed using SPSS 21. The results indicated at high rates of breastfeeding initiation but low rates of exclusive breastfeeding at six months. The women that had not had any breastfeeding problems and the ones that had been informed through the mass media were much more inclined to practice exclusive breastfeeding. The research study suggested increased mass media distribution of breastfeeding knowledge and education on the management of breastfeeding difficulties.

Hugelius et al. (2019) conducted a review of humanitarian radio usage in enhancing health and resilience in case of a natural disaster. The study determined that radio is an effective means of distributing health information, providing psychosocial support, increasing engagement with the community, and resilience by conducting an analysis of scientific and grey literature. The authors gave a suggestion of incorporating radio into disaster health response strategies. This observation can be further corroborated by other points of view that radio is still a cost effective and an accessible means of health communication.

Lastly, Tampah-Naah et al. (2019) investigated qualitative interview studies on maternal barriers to exclusive breastfeeding and supplemental feeding in Ghana. Thematic analysis brought forth spatial, societal and maternal constraints such as work requirements, housework, family pressure, health issues and food inaccessibility. The research advised the use of collaborative systems of support that included partners, families, institutions, and community health volunteers.

All these studies together indicate that the knowledge, cultural beliefs, gender roles, institutional support, health communication strategies, and media exposure have an influence on the practice of exclusive breastfeeding. They also affirm that radio and broadcast media are useful channels to be used in delivering health information dissemination and behavior change. Nevertheless, most of the research is either health facility or national based and little has been done on community-specific radio interventions of rural women. This breach highlights the importance of future research in the specific role of community radio in influencing exclusive breastfeeding awareness, attitudes, and practice in specific communities.

Summary of Literature Review

The crux of the study was on the effect of radio campaign in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas. The study looked at the various concepts that herald the subject matter of the study such as concept of radio and the concept of exclusive breastfeeding. The study also looked at the various issues concerning breastfeeding in Nigeria. Various studies were empirically reviewed to elicit the views of other scholars on the subject matter. Despite the fact that other studies extensively discussed the issue of exclusive breastfeeding in among Nigerians, none narrowed it down to the use of radio considering the impact and utilisation of radio among rural dwellers hence this study is meant to fill the yawning gap.

Methodology

Research Design

Research design has to do with different approaches adopted by a researcher in tackling a research topic. It is concerned with using a stated method or methods to study a phenomenon as to solve a given problem.

Survey research method is defined as "the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions" (Check & Schutt, 2012). This type of research allows for a variety of methods to recruit participants, collect data, and utilize various methods of instrumentation. In this study, this research methods will also involve structuring and administering questionnaires to the representative sample of the study. The questionnaire was used to further the overall analysis of the findings of this study for validity.

Area of the Study

The area of study for this work are residents of Enugu North and South Federal Constituency. This area was studied to ascertain the effect of radio campaign in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas.

Population of the Study

Population involves a group of persons or aggregate items, things the researcher is interested in getting information from for the study". Therefore, the population of this study was drawn from the residents of Enugu North/South Federal Constituency. According to the 2006 National Census Figure released by the Nigerian Population Commission (NPC), the population figure of Enugu North was 244852 while Enugu South was 198723. $244852 + 198752 = 443604$.

However, to get the actual current population of Enugu North and South Federal Constituencies, a 2.39% population was worked out from the 2006 census figure released. According to Nigerian Population World meters, the average annual population growth rate of Nigeria is 2.39%.

Thus:

$$\frac{2.39}{100} \times \frac{X}{1} \times 443604 = 10602.1356$$

$$= 10603$$

That is the yearly projected population growth figure. Therefore, projected figure was multiplied by 18.

Thus:

$$10603 \times 18 = 190854$$

The population of study now is;

$$190854 + 443604 = 634458$$

Population of study = 634458

Sample Size

The sample for this study was derived from the population using online Australian sample size calculator stated thus:

Therefore, the sample size is **400**.

Sampling Technique

The researcher made use of cluster sampling techniques. The cluster sampling technique is used when it is either impossible or impractical to compile an exhaustive list of the elements that compose the target population. With cluster sampling, one can divide a state into districts, villages and select groups of people from these areas (Nwodu, 2006, p.99)

This technique is relevant to this study considering the fact that the areas of study is made up of various areas, which are to be used as part of the study sample. This technique will enable the researcher to have a proper representation of the whole area that fall within the study area and sample. The sampling was done by dividing Enugu North/South Federal Constituency into clusters which is done in phases.

Enugu State			
Enugu State	Phase 1:	Enugu State	
	Phase 2:	Enugu North Federal Constituency	Enugu South Federal Constituency
	Phase 3:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Asata Township 2. China Town 3. G.R.A 4. Ogui New layout 5. Ihewuzi 6. Independence Layout 7. New Haven 8. Ogbette East 9. Ogbette West 10. Ogui Township 11. Onu-asata 12. Udi Siding/iva Valley 13. Umunevo 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Achara Layout East 2. Achara Layout West 3. Akwuke 4. Amechi I 5. Amechi II 6. Awkunanaw East 7. Awkunanaw West 8. Maryland 9. Obeagu I 10. Obeagu II 11. Ugwuaji 12. Uwani East 13. Uwani West
			In the 26 cluster/wards areas in Enugu North and South Federal Constituency, the researcher distributed 25 copies of questionnaire were distributed to each of the cluster/wards.

Measuring Instrument

This study used a formal questionnaire to collect data, which resulted in efficient and consistent responses. The questionnaire was distributed by hand to the respondents, who were instructed on how to fill it out in a way that effectively addresses the study's hypotheses and research problem. The questions were structured in both closed- and open-ended formats.

Primary sources of data were gathered for this investigation. The primary data was obtained by means of a questionnaire. Every one of the four hundred respondents in the sample received a copy of the questionnaire at random. To prevent ambiguity, the questionnaire's questions were properly structured.

Data in this study will be analysed using descriptive statistics, frequency and percentage, for the demography of respondents and research questions. The Chi-square formula will be used to test the hypotheses.

Data Presentation and Analysis

At the course of this study, the researcher administered four hundred (400) questionnaires. However, the returned copies of the questionnaire are three hundred and seventy five (375) copies. The tables below give a description and presentation of the demographic details of the respondents.

Demographic Data Presentations

The tables below give a description and presentation of the demographic details of the respondents.

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Male	247	65.9%
Female	128	34.1%
Total	375	100%

(Source: Field Survey 2024)

The table indicates that 247 of the respondents representing 65.9% are males, while 128 of the respondents representing 34.1% are females.

Table 2: Age of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
20 – 25	80	21.3%
26 – 30	188	50.1%
31 and above	107	28.6%
Total	375	100%

(Source: Field Survey 2024)

The table indicates that 80 of the respondents representing 21.3% are between the age of 20 and 25; 188 of the respondents representing 50.1% are between 26 and 30 years, while 107 of the respondents representing 28.6% are 31 years and above.

Table 3: Marital Status of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Single	50	13.3%
Married	325	86.7%
Total	375	100%

(Source: Field Survey 2024)

The table indicates that 50 of the respondents representing 13.3% are single, while 325 of the respondents representing 86.6% are married.

Table 4: Educational Qualification of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
O' level	85	22.7%
OND	28	7.5%
HND/Degree	179	47.7%
Others	83	22.1%

Total	375	100%
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(Source: Field Survey 2024)

The table indicates that 85 of the respondents representing 22.7% are O' level holders; 28 of the respondents representing 7.5% are OND holder; 179 of the respondents representing 47.7% are either HND or Degree holders, while 83 of the respondents representing 22.1% are of other qualifications not included in the options or have no qualification at all.

Table 5: Occupation of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Civil Servants	192	51.2%
Business person	102	27.2%
Teacher/Lecturer	60	16%
Others	21	5.6%
Total	375	100%

(Source: Field Survey 2024)

The table indicates that 192 of the respondents representing 51.2% are civil servants; 102 of the respondents representing 27.2% are business persons; 60 of the respondents representing 16% are teachers or lecturers, while 21% of the respondents representing 5.6% are of other occupation not mentioned in the variables.

Table 6: Religion of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Christians	286	76.3%
Muslims	24	6.4%
Pagans	65	17.4%
Atheist	Nil	Nil
Total	375	100%

(Source: Field Survey 2024)

On religion, 286 of the respondents representing 76.3% are Christians; 24 of the respondents representing 6.4% are Muslims; 65 of the respondents representing 17.4% are pagans, while none is an atheist.

Table 7: To what extent is radio campaign used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Great Extent	151	40.2%
Very Great Extent	81	21.6%
Low Extent	93	24.8%
Very Low Extent	50	13.3%
Total	375	100%

Field Survey 2024

The table indicates that 151 of the respondents representing 40.2% said that radio campaign is used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency to a great extent, 81 respondents, representing 21.6% said to very great extent, 93 of the respondents representing 24.8% have low extent, while 50 representing 13.3% of the respondents said to a very low extent.

Table 8: Does radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	115	30.6%
Strongly Agree	93	24.8%
Disagree	107	28.5%
Strongly Disagree	60	16%
Total	375	100%

Field Survey 2024

The table indicates that 115 of the respondents representing 30.6% agreed that radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural, 93 respondents representing 24.8% strongly agree, 107 representing 28.5 respondents strongly disagree while 60 of the respondents representing 16% said strongly disagree.

Table 9: Do women in rural areas comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	95	25.3%
Strongly Agree	94	25%
Disagree	92	24.5%
Strongly Disagree	94	25%
Total	375	100%

Field Survey 2024

The table indicates that 95 of the respondents representing 25.3% agree of the opinion that women in rural areas comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns; 94 of the respondents representing 25% strongly agree, 92 of the respondents representing 24.5% disagree while 94 representing 25% strongly disagree.

Analyses of Data

The data were presented and analysed according to research hypothesis of the study, using tables, frequencies and percentage.

Hypothesis One

H₁: Radio campaign is extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency.

H₀: Radio campaign is not extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency.

Table 10: Test of Hypothesis One

Variables	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
Great Extent	151	94	57	3249	34.5
Very Great Extent	81	94	-13	169	1.7
Low Extent	93	94	-1	1	1
Very Low Extent	50	94	-44	1936	20.5
Total	375				57.7

Field Survey 2024

Df = K - 1
 Df = 4 - 3

$$Df = 1$$

Level of significance at 0.05 = 9.488

Decision: Since the calculated Chi-square value (57.7) is greater than the table value (9.488), the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. It holds that Radio campaign is extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency.

Hypothesis Two

H_2 : Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas.

H_0 : Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding do not have significant effect on women in rural areas.

Table 11: Test of Hypothesis II

Variables	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
Agree	115	94	61	3721	39.5
Strongly Agree	93	94	-1	1	1
Disagree	107	94	13	169	1.7
Strongly Disagree	60	94	-34	1156	12.2
Total	375				54.4

Field Survey 2024

$$Df = k - 1$$

$$Df = 4 - 3$$

$$Df = 1$$

Level of significance at 0.05 = 9.488

Decision: Since the calculated Chi-square value (54.4) is greater than the table value (9.488), the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted while the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. It holds that Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas.

Hypothesis Three

H_3 Women in rural areas comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns.

H_0 Women in rural areas do not comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns.

Table 12: Test of Hypothesis Three

Variables	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
Agree	95	94	1	1	1
Strongly Agree	94	94	0	0	0
Disagree	92	94	-2	4	0.04
Strongly Disagree	94	94	0	0	0
Total	375				1.04

Field Survey 2024

$$Df = k - 1$$

$$Df = 4 - 3$$

$$Df = 1$$

Level of significance at 0.05 = 9.488

Decision: Since the calculated Chi-square value (1.04) is lesser than the table value (9.488), the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is rejected and the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted. It holds that Women in

Discussion of Results

In all, three hypotheses were tested for statistical support. All the alternative hypotheses tested positive. The focus of hypothesis one is on whether Radio campaign is extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency. In the analysis, the calculated Chi-square value (57.7) was observed to be greater than the table value (9.488), validating the alternative hypothesis. It holds that Radio campaign is extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency. Radio has also been used to preach about the importance of family planning, maternal and child mortality as well as exclusive breastfeeding which has been adopted by many homes. There is a lot of disinformation and misinformation, so people still want to check if it is not said on radio then it is not fact. That is why radio is popular and celebrated in Africa (Mutsaka and Satchel, 2023).

In hypothesis two, the focus was on whether Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas. The analysis showed that the calculated Chi-square value (54.4) is greater than the table value (9.488), authenticating the alternative hypothesis. It holds that Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas. Hugelius et al (2019) stated that radio also has the potential to cost-effectively reach a large number of affected people in areas with severely damaged infrastructure. Radio could, therefore, contribute to health recovery and wellbeing from both individual and community perspectives.

Hypothesis three dwelt on whether Women in rural areas do not comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns. In the analysis, the calculated Chi-square value (1.04) is lesser than the table value (9.488), giving credence to the null hypothesis. It holds that Women in rural areas do not comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns. Based on the foregoing, the outcome of this study is in consistent with Iheanacho, et al. (2021). It was discovered that in rural areas, problems of religion, superstitious beliefs, traditional and cultural practices still hinder effective exclusive breastfeeding in rural areas in Nigeria.

Summary

The focus of this study is on the Effect of Radio Campaign in Promoting Exclusive Breastfeeding among Women in Rural Areas (A Study of residents in Enugu North and South Federal Constituency).

The findings of the study is therefore summarised as follows:

1. Radio campaign is extensively used in promoting exclusive breastfeeding among women in rural areas in Enugu North Federal Constituency.
2. Radio campaigns that promote exclusive breastfeeding have significant effect on women in rural areas.
3. Women in rural areas do not comply to exclusive breastfeeding as a result of radio campaigns.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have necessitated some conclusions to be drawn from it. Having explored messages from radio on exclusive breastfeeding, it is seen that enough and adequate strategic contents have been disseminated to get nursing and expectant mothers acquainted with the adoption of measures to ensure healthy living for the women and their children. The radio is very effective in

promoting maternal and infant health hence the promotion of exclusive breastfeeding. It has the capability of appealing to all categories of women – literate and illiterate, urban and rural dwellers alike. Radio communicates in dialects and uses the local language to reach the target audience. Mass media is generally a powerful means of socialising people towards maintaining a proper and adequate healthy living. This is because people’s attitude and behaviour towards health was seen to be basically changed because of exposure to media messages. However, the barrage of well packaged and designed messages on exclusive breastfeeding has been hindered by suppositious beliefs, religious and traditional beliefs as well as other primordial sentiments.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. Frequent and constant portrayal of information about exclusive breastfeeding should be disseminated to nursing and expecting mothers as to create more access to information on good health care practices. Again, government should organize a forum and publicise it through the media for medical practitioners to visit communities and hospitals during antenatal periods to educate women on infant and maternal health.
2. Radio as well as other broadcast channels should adopt a more strategic approach towards mobilising nursing and expectant mothers towards proper infant and maternal health care practices which exclusive breastfeeding is part of. Radio messages for rural women on exclusive breastfeeding should be created in languages and dialects the local people understand better.
3. Radio messages should be designed to change the orientation, attitude, behaviour, superstitious beliefs, and mindset of people in rural areas in a positive light in order to completely adopt exclusive breastfeeding. The media must always highlight the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding, not only to mothers but also husbands.

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